

THE EUNIVERSAL PORTUGUESE DEMONSTRATOR: FROM MV-LV COORDINATED IDENTIFICATION OF FLEXIBILITY NEEDS TO ACTIVATION THROUGH THE UMEI

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ABSTRACT

The EUniversal project, funded by the European Union, aims to establish a universal approach to the utilization of flexibility by Distribution System Operators (DSOs) and their engagement with new flexibility markets. To achieve this objective, the project team has focused on developing the Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI) concept. This paper presents an overview of the process of adapting grid core systems to interact with different market platforms and agents, which is a key aspect of the real-world demonstration set to take place in Portugal.

EUNIVERSAL PROJECT

The EUniversal project aims to overcome some of the existing limitations in using flexibility by DSO. It strives to achieve this objective via a Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI) to facilitate the procurement of flexibility services while bridging system-specific differences between relevant stakeholders, namely DSOs, Flexibility Market Operators (FMO), and Flexibility Service Providers (FSP) or aggregators.

All the foreseen communications between DSOs and market agents are expected to be performed through the system-agnostic UMEI, which is adaptable and modular to the specific user needs and requirements. The UMEI is the center of the generic architecture proposed for the three demonstrations where this concept will be tested (Germany, Poland, and Portugal).

BUSINESS USE CASES – PORTUGUESE DEMO

The Portuguese pilot will demonstrate four Business Use Cases (BUC) for congestion management and voltage control, as in Table 1. Flexibility services for congestion management and voltage control were designed over three timeframes: from long-term planning and maintenance planning to day-ahead operation planning. Figure 1 illustrates a general overview of the demonstrator architecture that will be described in this paper. The UMEI enables the interaction with two different market platforms: NODES Flexibility market platform and the N-

SIDE market platform. CENTRICA is the aggregator, managing the flexibility of Medium Voltage (MV) and Low Voltage (LV) clients.

Figure 1 – General interactions overview

Table 1 – Business Use Cases

	BUC name	Service
BUC1	Congestion management in MV grids for the day-ahead market (or between 1 to 3 days in advance)	Congestion management
BUC2	Integrated Voltage Control in MV and LV grids for the day-ahead market	Voltage control
BUC3	Contracting flexibility services to avoid voltage and/or congestion issues during planned maintenance action in MV grids	Congestion management Voltage control
BUC4	Congestion Management for medium and long-term grid planning through market mechanisms	Predictive congestion management

This demonstration tackles three significant problems related to flexible local markets:

1. MV and LV flexibility needs assessment and services procurement.
2. Standard communication approach with flexibility markets.
3. Coordination between medium/long-term and short-term flexibility market results.

DSO TOOLS

A multi-level preventive management framework was developed to enable DSO procurement of day-ahead market-based flexibility services for congestion and voltage control [1]. The main characteristics are summarized below:

- Capability to forecast for the next hours/day the network status and identify a priori potential MV and LV network constraints (voltage violations and congestions).
- Coordinated assessment of flexibility needs and mobilization of flexibility resources between MV and LV networks.
- Compatible with different market designs, continuous or auction-based with day-ahead and/or intraday activity.

The main tools involved in the procurement of flexibility services are:

- The LV Forecasting tool provides voltage and active power forecasts for each LV customer.
- The Data-driven Voltage Control tool (DdVC) will manage the LV grid, providing functionalities such as the definition of flexibility needs to solve voltage problems in the LV grid and the definition of limits for the flexibility trade between the LV and MV grids [4].
- The Medium Voltage Optimal Power Flow (MV OPF) will define preventive actions to solve, completely or partially, expected technical constraints violations in the MV grid using the DSO resources and the available flexibility [5].
- The Medium Voltage Flexibility Scheduler Tool (MV FST) continues the work of the MV OPF but by the definition of power flexibility needs [6].

The DSO tools developed in the project introduce two main innovations:

- A data-driven approach was followed for LV networks flexibility needs assessment, taking advantage of the historical data from smart meters and avoiding further need for installing monitoring and control equipment. It allows dealing with LV networks limited monitoring capabilities and inexistent or poor characterization of network topology and feeder electric characteristics.
- A concept of dynamic flexibility areas allowing zone aggregation of flexibility resources according to their impact on solving technical constraints. For each of the LV and MV zones identified, the amount of flexibility needed to solve the identified technical constraints is computed and shared with the flexibility market platform to provide relevant but simplified technical information to support the economical clearing.

UMEI-STANDARD COMMUNICATION APPROACH WITH FLEXIBILITY MARKET

AGENTS

The UMEI was created to simplify and harmonize communication between DSOs, FMOs, and FSPs [2]. It is based on a conceptual architecture design that integrates a combination of different APIs (Application Programming Interface) to connect DSOs and market participants with several flexibility market platforms. This approach allows communication without needing a central data hub or mediation platform. The UMEI is publicly available and can be tested and implemented by any stakeholder.

Figure 2 FMO (Flexibility Market Operator) and FSP (Flexible Service Providers) servers in UMEI displaying the Trading phase

MARKET PLATFORMS

Two Flexibility Market Platforms are being tested considering each market operator's market design, flexibility products and services as well as with distinct clearing methodologies: NODES and N-SIDE

NODES

NODES' integrated market design allows for flexibility to be offered across all grid levels [3]. After identifying the required flexibility for the specific grid problem, the DSO actively selects the most appropriate flexibility for the identified grid constraint regarding volume, location, and price. NODES' current market clearing methodology applies Pay-as-bid due to the limited market liquidity.

Within the Portuguese demonstrator, NODES provides its market design (Figure 3) and platform to facilitate coordinated access to available long-term and short-term flexibility (LongFlex and Shortflex acc. to NODES terminology) in the LV and MV grid for congestion management and voltage control in the geographic areas of Mafra NW of Lisbon and Alcochete (Table 4).

The horizon of the products varies from Day Ahead to weeks and months ahead according to each BUC (Table 4) as well as location-specific grid requirements. According to the NODES rule book, the procurement of ShortFlex is performed via activation through the matching of corresponding orders. LongFlex consists of the reservation of flexibility over a determined time period and the activation in the corresponding NODES ShortFlex market.

Figure 3 NODES integrated market design [3]

N-SIDE

The N-SIDE Local Flexibility Market Platform will ease the link between FSPs/aggregators and DSO through an auction-based mechanism. Flexibility bids will be submitted alongside asset constraints (shared by FSPs/Aggregator) and network constraints (shared by DSO).

The strength of the N-SIDE Local Flexibility Market is its advanced market clearing process that is based on state-of-the-art optimization models and algorithms. It can concentrate the liquidity of the market with a closed-gate mechanism, before clearing it by maximizing the social welfare while respecting the asset and network constraints. The output of the algorithm will give the optimal bid selection (that maximizes social welfare) which has also one of the lowest procurement cost achievable for the DSO. Moreover, the auction will be run when new needs have been shared, matching the offers shared from the FSPs. This allows for modularity in the clearing and ensures that no unnecessary operations are performed.

N-SIDE is based on a pool system with a pay-as-clear pricing mechanism. The selection of the FSP bids is made by the market platform. The clearing does not use detailed grid information. Therefore, the dynamic flexibility areas concept is proposed to allow an efficient selection of bids without grid topology awareness.

AGGREGATOR

To provide flexibility, CENTRICA is following these steps: flexible asset registration; aggregate available flexibility and obtain optimal bids (both amount and price) to be submitted to the market platform via UMEI; dispatch the accepted bid by FMO and monitor resources to make sure that the service is delivered; calculate and submit the baselines per portfolio into the market platform via UMEI; and finally collect meter reading data from DSO via UMEI (FSP server as shown in Figure 2).

CENTRICA needs to interact with each flexible asset (for reading sub-metering data and sending control signals). In this demo, LV customers are provided with Home Energy Management System (HEMS). Therefore, CENTRICA will remotely interact with flexible assets via HEMS. However, MV customers will be activated manually due to the lack of installed API at the premises of these

customers.

ORCHESTRATION FOR FLEXIBILITY PROCUREMENT

Figure 4 illustrates in a timeline the interaction between the DSO (i.e., E-REDES) and the different tools. The main steps are described in Table 2.

Table 2 -Main framework steps

Data collection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collecting daily load profiles from MV/LV substations 2. Collecting load and voltage profiles from smart meters 3. SCADA latest status of MV network switches, OLTCs, etc.
MV and LV day-ahead network status forecast	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. MV load and RES forecasts are computed by existing E-REDES tools 5. LV voltage and load forecasting
Computing day-ahead MV network control plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. MV OPF computes optimal plan for the next day considering DSO assets (OLTC, network topology, capacitor banks, energy storage)
Defining MV and LV flexibility needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. DdVC computes flexibility ranges at the MV/LV substation 8. MV FST computes MV flexibility needs (if MV technical constraints are detected) 9. DdVC computes LV flexibility needs (if problems at the LV network remain after MV planned control actions)
Sending flexibility needs to N-SIDE Flexibility Market	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The network operator obtains the preventive plan for the MV network assets and the MV and LV flexibility areas. 11. Shares the flexibility needs areas with the N-SIDE market platform through the UMEI.
Selecting flexibility offers from market platforms	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Gathers flexibility offers from market platforms through the UMEI. 13. In the case of the NODES platform, the offers will be selected by the DSO using MV FST and DdVC.
Validation of flexibility and update of DSO operation plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. If the determined flexibility does not allow to solve all the problems, MV OPF uses remedy assets (renewable generations and, if deemed necessary, some loads). 15. E-REDES requests the final preventive plan.

Coordination with medium and long-term flexibility market results

As referred before, long-term flexibility procurement is being tested in the demonstrator. Voltage and congestion management services are considered to postpone

Figure 4: Timeline of the daily interaction between the different tools, from the data provision by the DSO till the final MV and LV preventive plans.

reinforcement investments and improve operational security during maintenance actions. The results of the long-term markets are a flexibility quantity reserved for a given day(s). The reserved flexibility needs activated in the day-ahead market.

SYSTEM INTEGRATION ARCHITETURE

The coordination and integration of the described innovative tools is the conceptualization and development of the system architecture that will support the real demonstration. To that aim, a platform has been set up in Microsoft Azure Cloud to provide conditions for deploying the different components and establishing a resilient interconnection between them, (Figure 5). This is the platform for/where:

1. E-REDES will make available the necessary data daily.
2. Data exchange processes between the tools will be hosted.
3. Interactions between DSO and the flexibility market platforms through the UMEI.
4. Market results and historical data storage for KPI (Key Performance Indicators) calculation.

To ensure the safety of the proposed solution, the platform is divided into two areas with different communication requirements/constraints (Figure 5):

- **Area 1:** Dedicated to important systems that use customer data. This area is designed to contain both the information and the resources, so that is only accessible to key users of the project. The objective of this area is to ensure the isolation of the system from potential external threats.
- **Area 2:** Dedicated to communication with external platforms. The purpose of this area is to

ensure that a separated layer exists between the solution's "core" systems (Area 1) and the components responsible for communicating with external platforms.

Figure 5- High-level system architecture

PORTUGUESE DEMONSTRATION OVERVIEW

The selection of the demonstration sites was defined based on a distinct set of criteria and according to the BUC that will be tested:

- High percentage of voltage and load diagram availability from smart meters deployed in the demo area.
- LV grid's SS (secondary substation) equipped with a DTC (Distribution Transformer Controllers).
- Existence of MV and/or LV flexible assets connected to the demo area grids.
- Impact of the combined FSP asset's flexible load in the total LV feeder load/SS load/MV feeder load.
- Considerable MV load flexible contribution to MV feeder peak load.

Final selection led to the following demonstration sites:

- Valverde (a small village located in a suburban area of the Évora district)
- West zone of Portugal (two urban areas: Mafra and Caldas da Rainha)
- Alcochete (near Lisbon - Tejo River south bank)

Customers

All the LV customers have previously participated in the H2020 Sensible Project [7] and the H2020 Integrid Project [8], so they already had installed equipment: Smart Appliances like Water Heaters (WH), Photovoltaic Panels (PV), Battery Storage (BT), all of them controlled by a HEMS (Home energy management system). The clients with only a HEMS installed were given smart plugs connected to interruptible loads like electrical heaters or fans.

Table 3 – LV Customers

LV flexibility Assets	# LV Customers
HEMS	8
HEMS; PV	4
HEMS; PV; BT	13
HEMS; WH	1
Total	26

Contrary to what was done with the LV client's engagement, new demonstration participants had to be enrolled to test the coordinated mobilization of LV and MV flexibility. First the MV feeders to each the SS with enrolled LV clients are connected to where identified. List the MV consumers connected to the identified MV feeders and access their impact in the feeder Load Diagram and flexibility potential.

It was possible to enroll eight MV consumers, among them MV consumers like water and waste treatment plants, supermarkets, and university facilities.

MV producers were also enrolled. The list of six producers includes a photovoltaic plant, wind farms, a biogas, and one cogeneration.

The final distribution of demo areas per BUC and Market Platform is the one presented in Table 4.

Table 4 - Distribution of demo areas per BUC and Market platform

Demo	Market platform	BUC1	BUC2	BUC3	BUC4
Mafra	Nodes	x		x	
Alcochete	Nodes	x	x		x

Caldas da Rainha	N-Side	x	x		
Valverde	N-Side	x	x	x	x

CONCLUSIONS

This article presents the framework developed in the EUniversal Portuguese Demonstration that will take place in spring 2023. Even though integration tests were performed, the demonstration will examine the viability and the challenges related to MV-LV coordinated identification of flexibility requirements for grid services and the activation of every service via the UMEI.

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